

PERSPECTIVES ON USE OF TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING PROCESS

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The Internet creates unique conditions for acquainting students with the cultural diversity of the countries of the studied language, which, unfortunately, is not always the case for a traditional English textbook. The Internet also creates a natural language environment for students: the ability to use authentic texts, communication with native speakers. Also, the Internet can be used as an assistant in organizing communication not only with people from different countries, but also between classmates and a teacher.

Recently, it has become convenient and popular to create blogs or groups on social networks, where the teacher and students can post topics for discussion, interesting material, audio and video. And the guys, sitting at home in a familiar and comfortable environment, can read, watch, discuss, write comments without fear of making mistakes. This is an additional opportunity for real speech practice.

There are many free online materials (interactive exercises, podcasts, online communities), methods and techniques that help make it easier for the teacher to get effective results, bring variety to the learning process and give it liveliness. Educational Internet resources are aimed at the integrated formation and development of various skills in students. You can use ready-made tasks, you can create them yourself.

The use of an interactive whiteboard in the classroom greatly helps the teacher increase the effectiveness of teaching, as it provides enormous opportunities for presenting material. When working with an interactive whiteboard, students can simultaneously see, hear, speak, and write on it. All this undoubtedly contributes to a better assimilation of the material. The use of an interactive whiteboard stimulates the development of mental and creative activity, includes all students in the work.

On the one hand, students are undoubtedly pleased with the introduction of the use of modern technology in the lesson and get more pleasure from the exciting learning process. On the other hand, the teacher, using modern technologies, makes the lesson diverse and rich in form, as well as meaningful in the results.

Using and integrating various technologies into the learning process, the teacher develops his professional competencies more and more every day.

Multimedia technology empowers educators to abandon the routine types inherent in traditional teaching activities, giving them the opportunity to use intellectual forms of labor, free from the presentation of significant parts of educational material and routine operations related to working out skills and abilities.

The use of ICT in foreign language lessons makes it possible to present the material visually, contributes to improving the quality of teaching and reducing student fatigue. Technical teaching aids help the teacher to increase the rate of presentation of the material and to meet the needs and curiosity of students [1]. It is no secret that students love to study in computer classes, perhaps because the lessons there are held in an informal setting.

Students have the opportunity to apply their knowledge and skills in other conditions, and show their knowledge in the field of ICT. In this case, the assimilation of new material is

much faster and easier. The elements of the game in foreign language lessons in various tasks cause only positive emotions in students, which contributes to the practical consolidation of the studied material.

The use of project-based teaching technology in the classroom allows you to solve the main tasks of forming creative thinking, ensures the development of initiative and independence, students acquire communication skills, work in a group and individually, allows you to apply the knowledge gained in the learning process in solving practical problems [3].

Of course, it cannot be argued that the use of ICT will help solve all the problems in teaching a foreign language, but it is an effective tool against monotony. The computer allows you to increase the volume of language training, develops imaginative thinking, activates the regional knowledge of students. Undoubtedly, ICT helps to increase the interest of students in learning, improve the results of learning activities.

The use of ICT helps:

- Attract passive listeners to active work;
- To form the information culture of the student;
- To improve the quality of knowledge of learners and students;
- Make classes more visual and interesting;
- To activate the cognitive interest of students;
- Implement student-centered and differentiated learning approaches;
- Discipline the teacher himself, form his interest in work;
- Activate thought processes (analysis, synthesis, comparison, etc.).

Computer technology opens up new opportunities for us. The material filmed with a camcorder can be processed on a computer: enter product images into a computer using a scanner, illustrations from prints, photographs, eliminate defects, select the desired format, change color, brightness, contrast, remove unnecessary details, cut out individual fragments and compose from them new images.

Such a system assumes a lot of preparatory work in drawing up a lesson, which, as a result, you can get an effective and universal system of teaching and testing knowledge. Electronic presentations enable the teacher of a foreign language to prepare visualization for the lesson.

Thus, students have a sense of the reality of events, as well as an interest and desire to learn more. Creation of the effect of presence: "I saw it myself!" is one of the most important advantages of interactive lessons. After such bright and lively lessons, students coming to school often ask "What will be new today? What's interesting?". This means that the children are motivated to learn. And one of the most important tasks of a teacher is to develop and maintain this motivation.

Data collection.

In order to study in detail the role of ICTs in educational activities, as well as to prove their impact on the educational motivation of students, we decided to conduct a survey among students of the 1st and 2nd years of Karakalpak State University as well as teachers and find out how technologies affect the educational process, and what variety they bring to the lessons.

Purpose: to get the opinion of the students of the university about the role of ICTs in increasing the motivation to learn. Opportunities to acquire spoken English through the

technologies are numerous and can be regarded the main solution to the problem. The purpose of this research is to investigate a study of how teachers can apply technologies in teaching English in order to increase student learning motivation.

Methodology – 50 students and 35 teachers of the university completed a questionnaire on developing communicative competence and motivation to learn the target language with the help of modern technologies. The information was supplemented with interviews and classroom observation.

The major aim of this study was to explore the methods and strategies applied in the learning process and increasing student motivation through ICTs in the university in Nukus. We were interested to find out what methods English teachers used to evoke students' interest to learn, what challenges they faced in motivating students and what kind of assistance they thought they needed to better prepare them for classes with ICTs.

Overall, 50 1st and 2nd year students and 35 teachers, aged 23-45, agreed to complete the questionnaire on their learning and teaching experience as well as challenges they faced using ICTs as a tool for student motivation.

Data analysis and results.

Results suggest that classes using ICTs reflect the perspectives on use of information and computer technologies in foreign language teaching and reveals the enormous possibilities of using a computer as an effective motivation tool.

Computer training programs allow teachers to train various types of speech activity and combine them in different combinations, to understand linguistic phenomena, contribute to the formation of linguistic abilities, create communicative situations, automate linguistic and speech actions, and also ensure the implementation of an individual approach and the intensification of independent work of learners.

Thanks to the use of information technology in the English language classes, the teacher is able to achieve from the learners the reproduction of information not on a reproductive, but on a meaningful, creative level, which will certainly be reflected in the quality of teaching.

The findings of this paper indicate that besides the advantages of using ICTs there are also major problems which most students and teachers have to face:

- many students and teachers do not have a home computer, and not all schools have time for independent study in computer classes.
- teachers do not have enough time to prepare for a lesson that uses computers.
- insufficient computer literacy of the teacher.
- lack of contact with the teacher of informatics.
- teachers do not have time to explore the possibilities of the Internet in their work schedules.
- lack of a demo center.
- it is difficult to integrate a computer into the lesson structure of lessons.
- division of the class into groups is not provided for when conducting a lesson in a computer class.
- not enough computer time at all.
- the school timetable does not include time for using the Internet in class.
- with insufficient motivation to work, students are often distracted by games, music, checking the characteristics of the PC, etc.

There is a possibility that, being carried away by the use of ICT in the classroom, the teacher will move from developmental teaching to visual-illustrative methods.

However, the use of ICT is justified, since it makes it possible to intensify the activities of students, makes it possible to improve the quality of education for students with low motivation, improve the professional level of a teacher, and diversify the forms of interpersonal communication of all participants in the educational process. And also, ICT tools used in modern education make it possible to achieve high results in learning.

New technologies make it possible to ensure interaction between teacher and student in the system of open and distance learning. The use of various ICT tools in the educational process can lead to both positive and negative consequences. In the context of the impact of ICT on educational processes, a type of modern teacher is formed, who must not only possess knowledge in the field of information and communication technologies, but also be able to apply them in their own professional activities; - under these conditions, a different type of student is emerging, who cannot imagine his life without a personal computer and the World Wide Web, the Internet, using the capabilities of modern technologies as information sources. But it is necessary to restrict access to information resources, to create conditions for the creative and research activities of students with different levels of development.

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